

Research in transformation: a pragmatist perspective on change-oriented research in digital education contexts

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ABSTRACT

The digital transformation creates persistent pressure for change in educational institutions and practice. Researchers actively involved in these digital change processes face specific methodological challenges that have so far been seldom discussed. Drawing on pragmatist methodology, this paper identifies and outlines key areas for methodological reflection that follow from the interlocked dynamics that characterize change-oriented research in education. Pragmatism proves productive for this endeavor due to its situational methodology and its socio-historical perspective on research. We identify seven reflection areas, each bridging methodological concerns with the social, political, and educational issues at stake: the digital transformation of research methods themselves, underlying assumptions of educational quality, appropriate generalization strategies, consideration of uncertainties and side effects, actor configurations, overlapping temporalities, and challenges to common wisdom. We discuss why each of these aspects points to important methodological issues and demonstrate how these reflection areas enable more deliberate engagement with established frameworks for change-oriented educational research, such as Evidence-Based Practice and Design-Based Research. The proposed methodological reflection areas thus respond to the pressing need for more reflexive research designs and strategies when researchers are themselves embedded in the digital transformation processes they investigate.

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1. Introduction

The digital transformation puts educational institutions and practice under persistent pressure to adapt and develop. Educational researchers are often actively involved in the resulting change processes, typically driven by their intrinsic motivation to become actively engaged, but often also responding to external demands to provide guidance for transformation initiatives. In such change-oriented research contexts, scholars become embedded within the very processes they study. These processes are often tension-ridden since they involve various actors with competing visions of digital education, unfolding within institutional settings marked by what Tyack and Tobin (1994) call the ‘grammar of schooling’ – enduring organizational structures and cultural norms that tend to slow change in school education. Balancing one’s own scholarly engagement and interests (often with a critical edge and ambition) with the problem spaces of other actors involved as well as with institutional restrictions can be a demanding task (Horvath, Steinberg, and Frei 2023).

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From a methodological perspective, this immersive positioning creates complexities that extend far beyond traditional research design considerations, as researchers must simultaneously design rigorous inquiry and navigate political and practical commitments. Importantly, the digital transformation intensifies and multiplies existing challenges of change-oriented educational research and adds new ones through three interlocking dynamics: First, regarding research objects, new and dynamic phenomena to study emerge, such as algorithmic devices which may evolve fundamentally during the research process (Dourish 2016; Kitchin 2017). Second, concerning research methods, our toolkit is undergoing digital transformation itself, changing not only tools but also logics of inquiry, as seen in the shift from model-driven hypothesis testing to data-driven analytics (Diaz-Bone, Horvath, and Cappel 2020; Savage and Burrows 2007). Third, regarding the social configurations in which research takes place, novel actor constellations emerge, establishing new stakeholders such as EdTech companies as co-producers of knowledge (Macgilchrist 2019b; Ortegón, Williamson, and Decuyper 2024; Peruzzo, Ball, and Grimaldi 2022).

Our objective in this article is to outline key methodological concerns that follow from these dynamics and that are often sidelined in everyday research settings. In a nutshell, we ask how best to align methodological choices with the specific change context at hand (with their specific knowledge needs, the motivations and interests of involved actors, restraining and facilitating conditions, etc.) and the role one as a researcher aims to play in it (which may be more critical or more affirmative, more deeply involved or more distanced, for example). In our experience, the methodological challenges that emerge in such settings are seldom discussed or even considered in their full implications. Insufficient attention to these concerns may, however, lead to inconsistent research designs and misalignment of purposes and processes, as well as to frustration when things just do not seem to ‘fit together.’

This article is meant as a methodological reflection and position paper. Our goal is to identify issues that deserve more focused attention and debate, particularly because they point to aspects through which diverging interests and perspectives can become tangible and consequential. Accordingly, we aim to sketch an overall picture of the issues at stake, rather than immersing in single aspects of the problematic. We develop our argument from a pragmatist epistemological perspective (Barthe et al. 2013; Dewey 1938) that explicitly acknowledges the inevitable political and social entanglement of educational research, and hence also its unavoidable positionality in relation to the social phenomena it engages with. This perspective also allows us to integrate our own varying thematic and disciplinary backgrounds (media education and sociology of education).

From this pragmatist foundation, we identify seven areas for methodological reflection: (1) the digital transformation of research methods themselves; (2) underlying assumptions about educational quality and justice; (3) appropriate generalization strategies; (4) consideration of uncertainties and side effects; (5) actor configurations; (6) overlapping temporalities; and (7) challenges to established conventional wisdom. For each area, we provide specific guiding questions that researchers can use to navigate methodological decisions when designing and conducting change-oriented research in digital education.

These reflection areas help ensure methodological coherence and at the same time help define one’s role as (critical) researcher within complex actor constellations. The reflection areas can thus also guide deliberate and productive engagement with existing and well-established frameworks for doing change-oriented educational research, such as Evidence-Based Practice, Design-Based Research, or Research-Practice Partnerships (RPPs) (discussed in more detail in section 3.3). They allow for the identification of the specific challenges and opportunities these existing frameworks come with in any concrete digital change context.

This article thus bridges three strands of research and debate that have so far hardly been related to each other: improvement studies or change-oriented research perspectives, critical studies of digital education and EdTech, and pragmatist epistemology. In their combination, these three strands of scholarship allow us to draw a nuanced picture of the methodological particularities of change-oriented research.

We begin our discussion with a brief note on the research contexts that motivate this article. We then examine why the digital transformation creates distinctive methodological challenges for change-oriented research (section 3) and present our pragmatist epistemological framework (section 4), before discussing the seven areas requiring reflexive attention when designing research and defining our roles as researchers in digital change processes (section 5).

2. Scope and positionality

This article is motivated by our own experiences in various change-oriented research consortia in Switzerland and Germany. Such consortia bring together multiple institutions to address the multifaceted nature of complex educational transformation processes. This organizational form is becoming increasingly common precisely because the digital transformation creates complexities that exceed the capacities of any singular disciplinary or methodological perspective. Such consortium contexts are privileged settings for both noticing the specific methodological challenges of change-oriented research (due to frequent methodological justification required by their interdisciplinary and multi-methodological composition) and for recognizing the complexities of defining researcher roles in change processes (due to their manifold links to educational practice, administration, and politics). They provide abundant opportunities to experience why and how methodological choices regarding data, indicators, or analysis matter.

While our reflections emerge from large-scale consortia, we believe the methodological challenges we identify and discuss apply broadly to change-oriented research in digital education. At the same time, this positioning inevitably shapes what we attend to: our analysis draws primarily on experiences from Western European publicly funded education and research systems and emphasizes challenges that might be particularly salient in consortium-based research arrangements. Digital transformation manifests differently across contexts – varying substantially in infrastructural conditions, actor configurations, and platform ecosystems – making contextual adaptation essential rather than optional. The reflection areas we propose are designed to be adaptable across diverse contexts, but researchers working in different regional settings, educational sectors, or organizational arrangements should critically examine which aspects require modification to address their specific transformation dynamics.

3. Doing change-oriented research in digital education contexts

This article identifies essential methodological considerations for conducting change-oriented research in digital education settings. The specific change dynamics that the digital transformation creates for both practice and research form the starting point for this argument. In the following, we discuss the complexities that educational practice faces in this context and then turn to the challenging position of educational research in processes of digital change. Existing frameworks for doing change-oriented research are helpful resources for dealing with the resulting tasks and difficulties, but their immediate applicability is inherently limited.

3.1. The digital transformation of education: complex change imperatives

Contemporary discourse on digital education is shaped by problematic change narratives: proclaimed inevitable futures of education that follow from societal dynamics and technological determinism (Perrotta 2021; Rahm 2023; Smith and Fressoli 2021). While neither the diagnosis of inevitable futures nor technological determinism provides adequate frameworks for understanding educational change, it is important to note that the digital era does entail genuine and significant changes in school education. Drawing on Perrotta's (2021) principle of *underdetermination*, we recognize, however, that digital change is as hard to predict as it is to willfully plan: rather than following straightforward linear relationships, educational transformation emerges from complex

constellations or *assemblages* of actors, technologies, policies, and ideas. The term transformation refers specifically to such multi-level reconfigurations that reshape not just practices but underlying structures, relationships, and values in education – and create real pressure for change:

First, the digital transformation introduces new actor constellations into educational contexts. Platform operators, technology providers, and data analytics firms have become pivotal in school development (Kerssens and Van Dijck 2021; Ortegón, Williamson, and Decuyper 2024; Sefton-Green 2022), creating novel dependencies and power dynamics. Second, educational objectives and content are evolving, with increased emphasis on digital competencies, critical engagement with information, and ethical considerations regarding technology use (Baumgartner et al. 2016). Third, teaching and learning methods are changing as digital tools enable new forms of instruction, assessment, and collaboration (Selwyn et al. 2017). Fourth, the ‘boundaries of learning’ are shifting, with new configurations between in-school and out-of-school contexts, formal and informal, as well as online and offline learning environments (Erstad and Silseth 2023; Koh and Chen 2021).

3.2. The role of research in the contested field of digital educational change

Against the backdrop of these complex change imperatives, researchers are increasingly called upon to engage in educational transformation processes. Such engagement might be anchored in an intrinsic motivation to critically assess ongoing changes in collaboration with educational practice and politics or to do research ‘that matters.’ In many cases, however, this engagement responds to a demand: researchers are expected to provide both *guidance* for educational change processes and the *evidence* needed for effective transformations.

In this article, we speak of change-oriented research to specify these entangled research-practice-politics configurations (Yurkofsky et al. 2020). We use change rather than improvement to acknowledge that the developments at stake are not necessarily positive (Macgilchrist 2021) and also that they go beyond isolated interventions within stable contexts.

Change-oriented research involves dialogue and collaboration between actors with different forms of expertise and knowledge, requiring permanent negotiation of roles, contributions, and relationships. Operating in such multi-stakeholder arrangements can become particularly demanding for researchers in digital education contexts, as they simultaneously face fundamental shifts regarding epistemic authority. As Savage and Burrows (2007) already elaborated in their diagnosis of a ‘coming crisis of empirical sociology,’ the locus of legitimate epistemic interpretation is becoming increasingly decoupled from academic research, with platform operators, EdTech companies, and data analytics firms gaining influence in a new division of epistemic labor (Dishon 2017; Komljenovic 2021; Williamson 2019). But not only the *who*, also the *how* (data and methods) and the *what* (digital learning) of social research are undergoing profound change (Diaz-Bone, Horvath, and Cappel 2020). Relevant aspects of this digital transformation of social research and its methods are addressed in reflection area 1 (section 5.1).

Faced with the challenges of multi-actor collaboration in times of shifting epistemic orders, researchers can find guidance in various frameworks for doing change-oriented research that aim to structure engagement with educational practice in transformation processes. Navigating this diverse field of approaches while defining coherent research processes is our central concern for the remainder of this article.

3.3. The limited applicability of existing frameworks

While a comprehensive overview of existing frameworks for change-oriented research is beyond the scope of this article, several influential approaches deserve mention. They define the landscape in which researchers engaging in digital change projects need to move and position themselves. For critical EdTech scholars, this can be particularly challenging in relation to Evidence-Based Practice (EBP). EBP emerged in the late 1990s (Hammersley 1997; 2002; Hargreaves 1997) with the goal of

grounding educational politics and practice in rigorous research evidence, establishing randomized controlled trials as the gold standard for identifying ‘what works.’ In response to widespread frustration with the methodological, political, and practical limitations of EBP (Biesta 2010; Cowen 2019; Phillips 2019; Simpson 2017; 2018; 2019), a range of approaches emerged that Yurkofsky et al. (2020) categorize as ‘Continuous Improvement Studies.’ These include Design-Based Research (DBR), which organizes focused collaborative innovation in iterative cycles of design, implementation, and analysis (Barab and Squire 2004; The Design-Based Research Collective 2003). Research-Practice Partnerships (RPPs) structure long-term collaborations between researchers and educational practitioners (Coburn and Penuel 2016). Networked Improvement Communities (NICs) bring together diverse stakeholders around shared improvement goals, using principles from improvement science to test changes across multiple contexts (Bryk 2015). Lesson Studies involve teachers collaboratively planning, observing, and refining lessons, with researchers participating as facilitators (Lewis, Perry, and Murata 2006). All these frameworks differ in (1) how they understand valid, useful knowledge (methodological dimension) and (2) how researchers should position themselves in relation to other actors and the change process at stake (role dimension). Evidence-Based Practice offers the most explicit methodological prescriptions, defining randomized controlled trials as the ‘gold standard’ and establishing clear procedures for knowledge synthesis (Parra and Edwards 2024; Styles and Torgerson 2018; Thomas 2016). These procedures have been subject to extensive critique regarding both their methodological foundations and their political implications (see, e.g., Biesta 2010; Cowen 2019; Phillips 2019; Simpson 2019). From a methodological perspective, EBP’s focus on average treatment effects fundamentally misaligns with practitioners’ knowledge needs: educators require an understanding of what works for whom, in which contexts, under what conditions, how and why – that is, answers to questions of variance that meta-analyses of averaged effects cannot address (Simpson 2018).

In contrast, Continuous Improvement approaches, despite often being referred to as ‘methods’, typically do not provide ready-made methodological recipes. While they offer far richer frameworks for structuring cooperation between researchers and other actors than EBP perspectives (Yurkofsky et al. 2020), they leave key methodological decisions about research design, data collection, analysis, and interpretation to the researchers. Considering the complexities of the digital transformation, it hence becomes clear that researchers cannot simply *apply* DBR or implement an RPP; they need to actively adapt and develop appropriate research strategies.

Our experience in change-oriented research on digital education reveals several recurring patterns that further complicate straightforward application of any given framework. Thus, the proprietary nature of educational platforms often prevents the kind of transparent co-design that a DBR process, for example, would require, since researchers and practitioners cannot fully access, understand, or modify the core parts of what they are collaboratively developing (Hartong and Förtschler 2019). Further, digital change in education entails an interplay of everyday classroom settings with other levels and arenas of educational systems, requiring researchers to engage not only with teachers and students but also with school administrators, educational policymakers, platform providers, and technical intermediaries – coordination challenges that extend beyond the researcher-practitioner dyads that frameworks like RPPs typically envision. Additionally, temporal misalignments emerge as digital technologies evolve fast; thus, a DBR project may be designed around specific platform affordances that fundamentally change during the research process, or an RPP may establish long-term collaboration around problems of practice that become obsolete as new tools reshape educational contexts. Finally, different stakeholders bring different conceptions of educational quality and justice into collaborative processes – creating tensions that require methodological strategies beyond what established frameworks provide (Imdorf and Leemann 2023).

These practical challenges raise fundamental methodological questions. How can researchers maintain methodological transparency and control when working with proprietary platforms? How should researchers approach generalization when several actor groups with varying knowledge needs are involved? How can research designs accommodate temporal misalignments between

different actors and fields? How can competing quality conceptions be navigated and accommodated throughout the research process? Addressing these and other questions forms the core of section 5. First, however, we establish the pragmatist epistemological perspective that grounds our approach (section 4).

4. Pragmatist epistemology as a framework for methodological reflection

In this article, we address the methodological challenges change-oriented research faces through a pragmatist epistemological lens inspired by Dewey's understanding of social inquiry (Dewey 1938; Dewey and Bentley 1975). Dewey's recognition that inquiry methods evolve alongside social conditions provides a framework for understanding how research methodologies must adapt to the digital transformation and its accompanying social, political, and technological changes. This pragmatist lens also illuminates the complex decisions educational researchers face when engaging with diverse stakeholders – from educators to EdTech companies – and when navigating the politically charged terrain of the digital transformation.

Although Dewey is frequently cited in change-oriented research literature (as explicitly noted by Yurkofsky et al. 2020), these references typically remain methodologically superficial, failing to engage with Dewey's fundamental epistemological insights. In the following, we outline five key tenets of pragmatist epistemology. These tenets provide the foundation for the selection of reflection areas that we discuss in section 5.

4.1. Tenet 1: The situational and historical nature of inquiry

A core tenet of Deweyan pragmatism is its radically *situational* conception of inquiry (Brown 2012). Dewey defines inquiry as the controlled or directed transformation of an 'indeterminate situation' into one that is 'determinate in its constituent distinctions and relations' (Dewey 1938, 104). Inquiry emerges from uncertainty – from tensions and disruptions that interrupt the normal flow of experience and demand resolution. Importantly, it is in and through dealing with situational uncertainties that actors develop and test not only ideas about how to handle the situation at hand, but also about the rules and tools to apply during this process.

This has profound methodological implications. First, methods and logics for inquiry cannot be deduced from transcendental truth but are actively developed in concrete socio-historical contexts (Diaz-Bone 2014). Second, it sensitizes us to how methods developed in one situation are used in subsequent ones – implying uncertainty about their continued applicability. Third, it draws attention to the effects inquiry methods produce when applied to different *indeterminate situations*.

This situational perspective fundamentally reshapes how researchers approach the dual challenge of designing studies and defining their roles within digital education contexts. Among others, it becomes crucial when considering the digital transformation of research methods themselves (reflection area 1), as these methods evolve in their own specific socio-historical situations, or when facing manifold and tension-ridden temporalities of different fields of practice involved in digital education (reflection area 6).

4.2. Tenet 2: Continuity and no privileged epistemic position

The situational understanding already implies that scientific research is only one particular form of inquiry. Dewey (1938) argues that scientific research developed from everyday forms of inquiry. He sees no sharp division between scientific research and other epistemic practices. This continuity does not erase differences – scientific knowledge production defines problems differently and produces distinct forms of knowledge – but these differences do not warrant assumptions of superiority or epistemic privilege.

This continuity tenet emphasizes concrete concerns as well as the varying logics guiding inquiry in different fields of practice and consequences of privileging certain forms. In change-oriented projects, non-scientific purposes and uses are constitutive for research aims and designs. In digital contexts, the issue of continuity becomes even more apparent as educational technologies increasingly incorporate their own logics and practices of data collection and analytics, often informed by the epistemic orders surrounding big data and computational sciences (see, for example, Beer 2018; Brevini and Pasquale 2020; Buckingham Shum and Luckin 2019; Burrows and Savage 2014; Gillani et al. 2022; Savage and Burrows 2007).

For our reflection areas, the pragmatist tenet of *no privileged epistemic position* is, for example, relevant when thinking about how to navigate increasingly complex actor configurations (reflection area 5). Also, the continuity of situations requires us to think about how the knowledge we produce becomes effective in various situations – alerting us to uncertainties and potential side effects as essential epistemic considerations (reflection area 4).

4.3. Tenet 3: The entanglement of facts and values

Perhaps most fundamentally, pragmatist epistemology rejects the fact-value dichotomy that still implicitly structures much methodological thinking. Putnam (2002), following Dewey, argues that describing facts presupposes value judgments, while value judgments necessarily refer to factual warrant. This entanglement reveals that social research cannot be value neutral.

In change-oriented research, scholars inevitably confront this circumstance, often explicitly (Yurkofsky et al. 2020). Attending to practical problems and to possible consequences of findings requires reflection on ethical concerns and wider social realities (Sjölund et al. 2023). Further, we engage with fact-value entanglements when asking what exactly we contribute and what intended and unintended effects our research might produce (Zhao 2017). Crucially, these moral and political aspects of education research cannot be separated from methodological choices – selecting outcome measures, determining sampling strategies, or framing research questions are unavoidably also political decisions (Desrosières 2011; Lury 2021; Parkhurst 2017).

This entanglement becomes particularly significant in digital education contexts, where values embedded in platform architectures and their underlying data analytics may conflict with educational values (e.g., Avnoon, Kotliar, and Rivnai-Bahir 2024; Gray and Boling 2016; Regan and Jesse 2019; Scholes 2016). This entanglement is hence particularly relevant when considering implicit conceptions of educational quality and justice (reflection area 2) or when identifying points where research challenges conventional educational wisdom (reflection area 7).

4.4. Tenet 4: Plurality of epistemic and moral orders

Plurality assumptions are characteristic of pragmatist thinking (Putnam 1981; Thévenot 2007). If logics and methods of inquiry are not expressions of transcendent truth but collective historical achievements produced in concrete situations, we must expect several such logics to coexist – ‘more than one but less than many’ (Mol and Law 2020), in other words: *plurality*, but not *arbitrariness*. This applies not only to epistemic, but also to moral orders. In education, we must navigate several different, yet widely shared understandings of what makes ‘good and fair school education’ (Derouet 2000; Imdorf and Leemann 2023). These plural understandings inevitably shape methodological decisions – for example by influencing outcome measures or the ways in which we relate to other actors involved (more or less critical, more or less distanced).

The digital transformation extends this landscape of pluralities by introducing new values (see, e.g., Dishon 2017; 2021; Gray and Boling 2016; Murphy and Ydesen 2025) (such as optimization, personalization, efficiency) alongside traditional educational values (e.g., equity, community, critical thinking), creating novel methodological challenges, for example, when researching technologies that embody different value assumptions than their users (Avnoon, Kotliar, and Rivnai-

Bahir 2024; Regan and Jesse 2019). This will be discussed, among others, in relation to reflection area 2 (underlying assumptions of educational quality and justice). The plurality tenet will further be crucial for reflecting on appropriate generalization strategies (reflection area 3).

4.5. Tenet 5: The distance-engagement relationship

Finally, pragmatism offers resources for navigating the tension between critical distance and practical engagement – a challenge particularly acute in digital education contexts. By rejecting the ‘spectator theory of knowledge’ (Stine 1973), pragmatism fundamentally challenges the assumption that greater distance leads to greater objectivity. Instead, it suggests reflecting on how engagement can increase credibility, while remaining aware of how researchers both shape and are shaped by the contexts they study (captured in the concept of ‘transaction’, see Dewey and Bentley 1975). Pragmatism reframes critical distance not as ‘detachment to be achieved’ but as demand to acknowledge our ‘complex interiority’, which entails conscious engagement with other actors and their concerns rather than assuming some transcendent outside position (Boltanski 2011).

This task of positioning one’s research in relation to the complexities of the digital transformation defines the very motivation for the objective of this article: to propose key reflection areas that point to key methodological decisions while mattering for this positioning. We identify seven such reflection areas – to which we now turn.

5. Seven areas for methodological reflection

The seven reflection areas presented below identify key methodological issues that matter particularly in change-oriented research in digital education contexts. The presented reflection areas function as crucial *methodological interfaces* between research design decisions, political and practical positioning, and digital transformation challenges. All seven areas share important characteristics: they are easily overlooked despite fundamentally affecting research credibility, coherence, and transferability; they span key research elements from problem framing to presenting findings; they involve political, moral, and organizational considerations; and they are distinctively shaped by digital transformation dynamics.

The idea of reflection areas responds to the demand to move from ritualistic application toward thoughtful adaptation of frameworks for doing change-oriented research (Yurkofsky et al. 2020). They serve as means for self-sensitization and critical engagement – both when designing one’s own research and when evaluating findings from other change-oriented projects.

In the following, we outline for each reflection area how it relates to pragmatist epistemology, why it matters particularly in digital education contexts, and what it implies for research design and researcher positioning. In Table 1, we succinctly and comprehensively summarize all seven reflection areas, highlighting what we see as key aspects for the discussion in this paper. The first reflection area – the digital transformation of research methods – serves a foundational role, establishing how digital contexts fundamentally alter research configurations and create the conditions that make methodological reflection in the other six areas particularly crucial.

5.1. Area 1: The digital transformation of research methods

The digital transformation alters the ways in which researchers can (and already do) engage with educational practice during change processes: dashboards allow for real-time monitoring of developments (Jarke and Macgilchrist 2021; Verbert et al. 2020); interactive visualizations make complex patterns in data accessible to practitioners (Byrd and Asunda 2020; Lister et al. 2021; Williamson 2016); and digital platforms allow for bridging online and offline interaction in novel ways (Erstad and Silseth 2023; Greenhow and Lewin 2016), to name but a few examples. Digital tools broaden and deepen the possible forms of involvement and exchange, making them simultaneously more immediate (in time) and more distanced (introducing ruptures between virtual and physical spaces).

Table 1. Key aspects for our seven areas for methodological reflection in change-oriented research.

Reflection Area	Pragmatist anchoring	Digital Relevance	Research Design Implications	Role Definition	Examples of implications for working with frameworks
1. Digital transformation of research methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methods developed in socio-historical contexts • Methods entangled with organizational forms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New data infrastructures • Algorithmic opacity • Shifting epistemic authority • Novel epistemic values and virtues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data collection: navigate platform constraints and reduced transparency • Quality assurance: validate black-boxed processes where possible • Analysis: combine data - and model-driven analysis where appropriate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Novel tools for exchange and engagement • Black-boxed agents involved in change processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBP: assumes control over variables and interventions; requires stable contexts • Improvement studies: must navigate new platforms and opaque design principles
2. Assumptions of educational quality and justice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plurality of moral orders – several conceptions of good and fair education • Fact-value entanglement – research never neutral 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Values embedded in digital technologies • Marketing claims vs. actual tools • Tensions between competing educational values 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outcome measures: explicate and define value commitments • Sampling: include diverse perspectives on quality/justice • Data interpretation: handle value conflicts in findings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopt, critique, or mediate between competing values? • Enable debate about quality and justice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBP: relies on predetermined, standardized outcome measures that embed specific values • Improvement Studies: need explicit strategies for surfacing competing stakeholder values
3. Appropriate generalization strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plurality of epistemic orders • Continuity: no privileged epistemic position 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demands for different forms of transferability and generalizability • Tension: global platform ↔ local implementations • Data-driven methods challenging traditional generalization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategy selection: match research design to generalization needs • Multi-strategy designs: accommodate competing requirements • Validation: specify transferability conditions across contexts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mediating between stakeholders and their knowledge expectations and needs • Explicating generalization claims and their limitations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBP: defaults to experimental generalization without considering stakeholder knowledge needs • Improvement Studies: open to multiple strategies but provide insufficient selection guidance
4. Consideration of uncertainties and side effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Situationalism: knowledge needs depend on context • Attention to practical consequences, which hinge on situational factors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital tools with unforeseen and manifold consequences • Rapid, interconnected changes • Algorithmic opacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptive designs: warrant openness to emergent effects and changing conditions • Multi-method approaches: combine qualitative scrutiny with quantitative monitoring • Variation focus: prioritizes patterns of variation over averages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Balancing critical alertness to potential harms with constructive engagement • Raising awareness of inevitable uncertainties and possible side-effects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EBP: focuses narrowly on predetermined outcomes, obscuring sources of variation and side effects • Improvement Studies: offer iterative flexibility but require effort to explore unintended consequences

(Continued)

Table 1. Continued.

Reflection Area	Pragmatist anchoring	Digital Relevance	Research Design Implications	Role Definition	Examples of implications for working with frameworks
5. Actor configurations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuity: no privileged epistemic position Unique problematic situations requiring different forms of knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New stakeholders join traditional educational actors Actor groups differ in knowledge needs, values, and interests Shifting epistemic authority 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actor mapping: identify the role of actor groups across research stages Value clarification: explicate values, interests, and success criteria Control assessment: determine who influences key decisions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Critical friend, embedded collaborator, or boundary-spanner? Navigating tensions between academic, commercial, and practice-based interests 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EBP: assumes control over interventions and measurements as well as stable contexts Improvement Studies: struggle with overwhelming stakeholder complexity
6. Overlapping temporalities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Situationalism: rhythms and speed Plurality of epistemic logics and practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multiple conflicting timeframes Increased speed of change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temporal mapping: align research processes with stakeholders' time needs Stability assessment: determine needed design flexibility versus consistency Response timing: distinguish quick answers from long-term analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Balancing immediate implementation needs with longer-term knowledge development Managing expectations about time horizons among actors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EBP: assumes context stability and controlled timing Improvement Studies: face the challenge of coordinating diverging temporal demands and rhythms
7. Challenges to common wisdom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research as disruption of habitual thought Continuity and rupture of knowledge forms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prevalent narratives about technology and learning Marketing claims vs. educational realities Techno-deterministic assumptions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assumption identification: surface taken-for-granted beliefs requiring examination Enhanced rigor: empirical focus on points that challenge accepted wisdom Relationship management: balance critique with stakeholder engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Balancing critical questioning with maintaining collaborative relationships Creating spaces for joint examination of assumptions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EBP: constrained challenging capacity due to RCT requirements Improvement Studies: allows critical engagement but must balance critique with collaborative emphasis

Seen from a pragmatist perspective, however, more is at stake than just adding novel tools and possibilities to our repertoire for participation and exchange. Pragmatist epistemology sensitizes us to how research methods emerge and evolve within specific socio-historical contexts, becoming institutionalized over time into configurations of knowledge production. These configurations encompass not only dominant methods and analytical approaches but also entail organizational forms in which research is done (Diaz-Bone, Horvath, and Cappel 2020), epistemic values and virtues including criteria for scientific quality (Carrier 2013), or the social distribution of epistemic authority (Savage and Burrows 2007).

In the twentieth century, social research interlocked strongly with the national welfare state, favoring forms marked by high epistemic and political accountability, thus privileging academic knowledge production (Desrosières 2011; Porter 1996; Smith 1994). The digital transformation fundamentally challenges this established configuration in several essential ways. Thus, data-driven rather than model-driven approaches today dominate computational social sciences, with pattern discovery replacing hypothesis testing as the primary analytic strategy. This goes hand in hand with shifting epistemic values – for example favoring complexity over simplicity (Hossenfelder 2018), speed over rigor, or predictive accuracy over explanatory power (Alvarez 2016; Enni and Herrie 2021; Smithers 2023). Also, the organizational context in which research is done shifts to private companies that own data infrastructures and analytical tools (Bartlett et al. 2018). As a result, researchers lose control and transparency over crucial parts of the research process (Sahlgren 2023). Finally, traditional quality assurance procedures become difficult to apply when statistical chains increasingly include ‘black-boxed’ algorithmic elements (Brevini and Pasquale 2020; Pasquale 2015; Prinsloo 2020).

These transformations also challenge existing frameworks for doing change-oriented educational research. After all, these frameworks – from EBP to NICs – were all developed within and bear the marks of the epistemic configuration of the late twentieth century. Their underlying assumptions regarding data access, methodological control, and institutional arrangements thus become questionable in digitally transformed research environments. For example, key ideas of Evidence-Based Practice become problematic in the light of data worlds that neither allow for transparent operationalization of variables nor provide sufficient control (Gillani et al. 2022; Savage and Burrows 2007) to implement methodologically ‘clean’ Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs) (Parra and Edwards 2024; Styles and Torgerson 2018). Likewise, Design-Based Research faces difficulties when digital tools embody design principles that are not transparent and also not within the reach of educational actors involved in collaborative development processes. Finally, cooperation formats such as Research-Practice Partnerships or Networked Improvement Communities must navigate new power dynamics that encompass private business actors – with far-reaching implications for issues such as transparency or public accountability.

Scholars involved in change-oriented research in digital education contexts should therefore ask:

1. How does the research context differ from traditional (*schoolbook*) social research settings as they were established prior to the digital transformation?
2. What methodological implications follow from this divergence?

The discussion of the remaining six methodological reflection areas guides engagement with these questions by pointing to key methodological concerns.

5.2. Area 2: Underlying assumptions of educational quality and justice

Digital technologies and platforms embed specific conceptions of educational quality and justice that often remain implicit. These moral orientations create methodological challenges when researchers must decide which outcomes to prioritize and how to position themselves in relation

to potentially conflicting conceptions of what makes ‘good and fair’ school education (Imdorf and Leemann 2023).

Pragmatist epistemology offers two essential insights for navigating this challenge. First, the plurality assumption (Putnam 1981) sensitizes us to the existence of multiple legitimate conceptions of educational quality and justice that have evolved over time. Second, the entanglement of facts and values (Putnam 2002) reveals how research activities and instruments inevitably reflect political and moral commitments, from the definition of problems to the choice of outcome measures and the prioritizing of findings.

Digital contexts intensify the resulting challenges of aligning methodological choices and educational positions in distinctive ways. Any digital learning tool or environment mirrors educational values – such as the measurable outcomes prioritized by learning analytics dashboards or assumptions about learning progressions and student needs in adaptive learning apps, to give but two examples (Macgilchrist 2019a; Williamson 2017a). Digital technologies also add normative orientations from outside the educational field – such as efficiency and speed (Kohljenovic 2021) – that may conflict with the educational commitments they enact. Further, the quality frames that dominate the marketing of digital tools (e.g., creativity, self-fulfilment) often diverge from the values embedded in their algorithms (e.g., standardized achievement metrics) (Horvath and Steinberg 2023). The opacity of algorithmic systems complicates attempts to identify and engage with the resulting, potentially highly intricate value configurations (Gillani et al. 2022).

These digital complexities create particular challenges for existing change-oriented research frameworks. The plurality of underlying conceptions of quality and justice is an especially sensitive issue for EBP approaches which rely on clearly defined, unidimensional and standardized outcome measures. Similarly, when working with improvement studies frameworks, researchers need to develop explicit strategies for surfacing competing quality and/or justice conceptions among stakeholders and identify how these affect research designs and processes.

For change-oriented researchers, this raises several key questions:

1. What educational values are embedded within the digital technologies, platforms, and environments under investigation?
2. Do the value orientations implicit in different research design elements – problem framing, participant selection, outcome measures – align or conflict with each other?
3. What values do researchers bring to their work, and where do these potentially clash with the priorities of educators, policymakers, or technology developers?
4. Given such value tensions, which aspects of the research design require heightened scrutiny or modification to maintain credibility across stakeholder groups?

Whether working within EBP frameworks that rely on standardized measures or improvement studies that emphasize stakeholder collaboration, researchers must consciously examine how their methodological choices privilege certain educational values while potentially marginalizing others. They hence must decide whether to surface implicit value tensions, facilitate dialogue across competing conceptions, or advocate for educational values that might be marginalized in digital contexts.

5.3. Area 3: Appropriate generalization strategies

Change-oriented educational research typically engages with local contexts but must provide knowledge transferable across situations, be it that this knowledge is newly generated or that existing knowledge is made available for the contexts at hand. In methodological terms, any change-oriented research requires a generalization strategy. (We use the term generalization broadly to include not only statistical representativity but also qualitative strategies ensuring ‘transferability’ of knowledge (Williams and Tsang 2015).)

A pragmatist epistemological lens helps understand and address these questions by sensitizing us to three decisive issues: (1) the historical development of several distinct generalization strategies that are today firmly established, each suited to specific knowledge needs; (2) the differing epistemic values and quality criteria each strategy embodies, values that help organize and evaluate research on an everyday basis; and (3) how different actors in different situations require different types of knowledge – reflecting varying generalization needs.

Three canonical generalization strategies have, over the past decades, emerged in social research (De Vaus 2001; Firestone 1993; Little 1993). *Experimental generalization* aims at identifying isolated causal relationships through controlled designs (Hintikka 1988; Kirk 1993). *Survey generalization* detects patterns and prevalence across populations through representative sampling (Stern, Bilgen, and Dillman 2014). *Case study generalization* uncovers mechanisms and contextual dynamics through in-depth investigation of specific instances (Yin 2014).

The digital transformation amplifies the challenge of selecting appropriate generalization strategies in three important ways. First, digital contexts simultaneously generate demands for all three knowledge types, often depending on the actor groups involved: a school principal or an EdTech company might be primarily interested in experimental generalization, demonstrating the concrete pay-off (effect size) of a concrete measure for achieving some well-defined outcome; for educational administration, the priority may be on average effects that can be expected for their regional school populations (survey generalization); teachers, in contrast, often require an understanding of mechanisms and interactions in concrete classroom contexts (case study generalization). Second, digital platforms often operate across highly diverse contexts while implementation remains deeply local, creating tensions between global and contextual knowledge. Third, the digital transformation of research methods challenges established generalization logics; (big-)data-driven analytics and data mining techniques do not correspond to any of the three common forms of generalization in social research (Diaz-Bone, Horvath, and Cappel 2020).

Existing frameworks for change-oriented research rarely acknowledge the methodological challenges of generalization in digital contexts. Evidence-Based Practice approaches typically privilege experimental generalization by default, seeking causal knowledge transferable across contexts while showing little awareness of different knowledge needs between stakeholders and concrete situational contexts. Improvement studies frameworks are in general open to different generalization strategies but their emphasis on collaborative stakeholder engagement can obscure the fact that different stakeholders may require fundamentally different types of generalizable knowledge, creating methodological tensions.

For change-oriented researchers, this reflection area raises several key questions:

1. Which generalization strategy (experimental, survey, case study) best serves the primary research objectives?
2. What type of knowledge transfer do different stakeholders need or expect?
3. What tensions may arise between a project's generalization needs and the data infrastructures employed in digital change processes?
4. How can multiple generalization strategies be combined to address different needs and constraints?

This requires paying close attention to diverse stakeholder knowledge needs: policymakers typically require survey generalization to understand system-level patterns; school leaders might desire experimental generalization to justify resource allocation decisions; and teachers often benefit most from case study generalization that illuminates contextual implementation mechanisms. The multi-level nature of digital change often necessitates corresponding multi-level generalization strategies, with generalization choices functioning as both methodological decisions and positioning moves that shape researcher relationships with diverse stakeholders.

5.4. Area 4: Consideration of uncertainties and side effects

The digital transformation creates rapid, interconnected changes across educational practices, relationships, and institutional arrangements, as ongoing developments in artificial intelligence and data analytics demonstrate. For researchers involved in change-oriented projects, these dynamics have an important, but often neglected implication: the need for increased attention to potential side-effects (Zhao 2017; Zhao and Beghetto 2024) and uncertainties (Beghetto 2023; Macgilchrist and Jarke 2025) accompanying digital change.

Understanding how to navigate this complexity requires an epistemological perspective that acknowledges fundamental indeterminacy. From a pragmatist perspective, attention to uncertainties and side effects reflects the recognition that inquiry emerges from and responds to genuinely indeterminate situations (Dewey 1938). The pragmatist situational understanding alerts us to how educational technologies, once implemented, become entangled with existing practices, creating outcomes that are neither deterministic nor random but contingent on specific contextual configurations (Perrotta 2021). For example, digital learning environments generate unpredictable interactions between technological affordances, pedagogical approaches, and diverse learner characteristics. An adaptive learning platform might personalize content yet reshape classroom dynamics and redefine legitimate knowledge, while a learning management system might improve efficiency while unintentionally privileging certain subjects or approaches.

These examples of unintended and unforeseen dynamics demonstrate the need for designing research processes that allow researchers to remain alert to side effects and uncertainties. Methodologically, this is a strong argument for qualitative methods and case study designs (Yin 2014). However, experimental testing of possible harmful and detrimental effects or quantitative surveying of developments might also be needed (Beghetto 2023; Zhao and Beghetto 2024). Single research teams will rarely have the capacity to cover this methodological breadth, requiring collaboration and building on others' expertise.

These methodological requirements create particular challenges for existing change-oriented research frameworks. Evidence-Based Practice approaches typically focus narrowly on predetermined outcomes, obscuring sources of variability that matter most to practitioners (Simpson 2018). While improvement studies frameworks offer more flexibility, researchers must consciously harness their iterative structure to systematically explore unintended consequences. For change-oriented researchers, this raises several key questions:

1. What unintended effects might emerge in or from planned digital environments?
2. How can research designs systematically monitor for unforeseen consequences?
3. Which methods best capture variation and contingency rather than average effects?
4. What sources of uncertainty deserve particular attention in this context?

Regarding the task of defining our roles as researchers in collaboration, this reflection area highlights the need for balancing critical alertness with constructive engagement, especially when working with actors who may resist confronting uncertainties or harmful effects in change processes they have invested in.

5.5. Area 5: Actor configurations and relationships

The digital transformation reconfigures the actor landscape in which educational research takes place. Traditional actors – students, teachers, school leaders, administrators etc. – are joined, to name but the most important, by EdTech companies (Williamson 2022), platform operators (Komljenovic 2021; Sefton-Green 2022), data scientists (Buckingham Shum and Luckin 2019), technological and financial brokers (Davies et al. 2022; Komljenovic et al. 2023; Ortegón, Decuyper, and Williamson 2024; Ortegón, Williamson, and Decuyper 2024), and various other

intermediaries (Caves and Oswald-Egg 2021). These new configurations create distinctive methodological challenges for change-oriented research.

From a pragmatist perspective, we need to acknowledge that all these different actor groups face unique problematic situations that require different forms of knowledge or “evidence” (Lury 2021). Many are involved in their own epistemic practices and forms of inquiry. These practices differ in important regards, including their varying temporal horizons, incompatible success metrics, and diverging criteria for relevance and quality – thus, commercial actors will tend to value rapid development cycles and scalability highly, while quality and relevance for educational institutions will be linked to orientations towards slower, longer-term development and contextual adaptation.

These divergent epistemic orientations create concrete challenges for research design and researcher positioning. One obvious methodological implication concerns control over and ownership of data: novel actor constellations reshape what data can be collected, by whom, and how (Bartlett et al. 2018; Brevini and Pasquale 2020; Williamson 2017b). When educational processes occur within proprietary platforms, researchers lose control over crucial aspects of data collection (Hartong and Förschler 2019). A more subtle methodological issue concerns the epistemic values that guide research design decisions. Academic researchers will often value control and transparency, while teachers emphasize classroom applicability (Areljung, Leden, and Wiblom 2021). Novel actors such as developers and companies may, in contrast, prioritize criteria such as exploitability of metrics (e.g., on user engagement) (Horvath, Frei, and Steinberg 2025).

Equally important is how researchers define their position within these configurations – a core aspect for this article since any change-oriented research requires aligning research with practical agendas and balancing critical engagement with immediate practical relevance. In digital contexts, researchers face potentially tension-ridden expectations. Whether adopting roles as critical friends, embedded collaborators, or boundary-spanners, each position will have repercussions for methodological choices.

When engaging in change-oriented research, it is essential to be aware of the points at which we as researchers might struggle with these complexities when relying too firmly on single existing frameworks. Thus, EBP approaches must presume researcher control over both interventions and outcome measurements, which are further expected to remain stable over time – presuppositions that quickly become untenable when dealing with a multiplicity of stakeholders. Improvement studies frameworks that emphasize collaboration and participation in research activities will often face the overwhelming complexity of diverging incentive structures and relevance criteria associated with different stakeholder interests.

Researchers involved in digital change should therefore consider the following questions:

1. What actor groups are involved in what stages of the research?
2. In what regards do involved actors differ in their priorities, epistemic values, knowledge needs, and success criteria?
3. What parts of the research design are affected by varying interests and orientations (choice of outcome measures, groups to include, presentation of findings ...)?
4. How should researchers position themselves in case of competing stakeholder interests and power dynamics?

5.6. Area 6: Overlapping temporalities

The digital transformation reconfigures temporal dimensions of educational practice and research in ways that deserve careful methodological attention (Hartong, Decuyper, and Lewis 2025; McLeod 2017). Multiple conflicting timeframes emerge that are simultaneously active: algorithms operate in real-time, technological capabilities evolve quarterly, pedagogical practices develop over academic years, and institutional change unfolds across multiple years. Importantly, new actors and

stakeholders introduce their own temporal dynamics – such as EdTech companies driven by rapid development cycles and market timelines (Horvath, Frei, and Steinberg 2025). These temporal misalignments create fundamental methodological challenges for change-oriented research.

Pragmatist epistemology recognizes inquiry as inherently temporal – unfolding as a process that relates problem identification, idea development, reasoning, and practical testing in specific situations (Brown 2012). Accordingly, different fields of (epistemic) practice develop their own distinctive rhythms, creating situation-specific temporalities that researchers must navigate without imposing artificial uniformity.

The digital transformation of research affects temporality in two crucial ways. First, it transforms the temporal order of knowledge production itself – for example, data-driven approaches often begin with pattern discovery before theoretical framing, inverting the traditional sequence of theory-driven research. Second, concerning objects of inquiry, digital contexts create the methodological challenge of studying technologies that fundamentally transform during the research process, as with AI systems that might evolve from rule-based to generative during a multi-year study.

The methodological implications of these combined dynamics become obvious when thinking about time-related aspects of existing frameworks for change-oriented research. Evidence-Based Practice embeds specific temporal assumptions: stability of interventions across time, controlled exposure time to interventions, and precisely timed pre/post measurements to discern short-, mid-, and long-term effects. These methodological requirements become increasingly difficult to satisfy when studying rapidly evolving digital environments, as it becomes more and more complicated to stipulate the required intervention and research schedules in increasingly complex actor configurations. Improvement study frameworks offer more design flexibility through their cyclical, iterative nature. This methodological advantage however comes at the price of complications when multiple research components (each with their own temporal demands) must be coordinated – and these must be arranged with diverse actor temporalities.

These temporal misalignments require researchers to navigate competing time pressures while maintaining methodological coherence. This involves identifying where research designs need stability versus flexibility, and where stakeholder temporal demands align with or conflict with methodological requirements. The following three guiding questions help tackle these issues:

1. What are the different time horizons and rhythms of key stakeholders in this project?
2. At what points do challenges occur for research designs due to lack of stability (e.g., rapid technological developments) or too much inertia (e.g., institutional regulations)?
3. Which aspects of the research require quick responses to stakeholders, and which require longer-term analysis to support meaningful change?

5.7. Area 7: Challenges to common wisdom

The digital transformation of education involves widespread narratives and assumptions about technology, learning, and change that often go unexamined despite their influence on practice. Whether addressing dystopian views of digital tools or uncritically accepted marketing claims, researchers must develop specific methodological approaches to examine and potentially disrupt established conceptions effectively.

From a pragmatist perspective, the challenge of established assumptions is directly linked to the *raison d'être* of social research. If science cannot claim a privileged epistemic position, the question emerges about what researchers can contribute to change processes that other actors are not themselves capable of. Pragmatist thinking sees this added value in the capacity to disrupt habits of thought. What we as researchers effectively 'contribute' often lies in our capacity to methodically examine what seems self-evident.

Importantly, challenging common wisdom is not merely about having a critical orientation but involves specific methodological tasks. Researchers must design studies that can surface tacit assumptions, examine how established conceptions simplify complex phenomena (and with what consequences), and pay special attention to warranting claims that other actors might find doubtful.

In digital education settings, these tasks take on distinctive forms. For instance, research on adaptive learning platforms must address the disjunction between marketing claims of ‘personalization’ and the reality of standardized achievement scales encoded in algorithms (Dishon 2017; 2021; Dumont and Ready 2023; Horvath, Frei, and Steinberg 2025; Regan and Jesse 2019; Skarpenes and Hidle 2024; Williamson and Piattoeva 2019). This requires methods that allow comparing algorithmic functioning to stated intentions (e.g., through ‘walkthroughs’, Light, Burgess, and Duguay 2018; Troeger and Bock 2022; see also Baker and Hawn 2022; Kitchin 2017; Gillani et al. 2022; Prinsloo 2020). Similarly, research on learning management systems needs methods to surface tacit assumptions about teaching and learning, examining how these systems reshape pedagogical relationships and knowledge authority beyond the common focus on administrative efficiency (Enni and Herrie 2021; Gray and Boling 2016).

Existing frameworks for change-oriented research handle the methodological task of challenging presuppositions in markedly different ways, with significant implications for research design. Evidence-Based Practice approaches are fundamentally constrained in this regard, as they methodologically depend on keeping contexts of the tested intervention stable. While improvement studies frameworks provide more space for critical engagement, they come with their own challenges of balancing critique with the collaborative relationships these approaches emphasize. The methodological implications hence extend to researcher positioning as well. Challenging established conceptions increases potential research value but risks threatening relationships of trust and shared understanding essential to change-oriented projects.

These methodological considerations require researchers to balance the critical examination of assumptions with the maintenance of productive stakeholder relationships in collaborative change processes. This involves strategic decisions about which assumptions to examine, where to apply additional methodological rigor, and how to navigate potential tensions with collaborators. For change-oriented researchers, this raises several key questions:

1. What taken-for-granted assumptions about digital learning need systematic examination in the given research context?
2. Where do (potential) challenges to common wisdom require particular methodological scrutiny and empirical grounding?
3. At what points will researchers need to balance critical examination with maintaining collaborative relationships?

6. Conclusion: toward reflexive methodology in digital education research

This article started from the observation that designing reflexive and relevant educational research in contexts of digital change is a challenging task. Our key argument is that this task cannot be productively tackled by sticking to ready-made recipes for conducting change-oriented research, whether in the EBP tradition of ‘What works’ or in one of the established Continuous-Improvement Studies frameworks. Rather, we need approaches that allow for adaptivity and context-sensitive research design, as well as for actively defining one’s own role as engaged scholars.

To this end, we propose to base research-design decisions in reflections on seven key areas in which the social phenomenon studied, the methods and data available, and the change ambitions involved intersect. In a nutshell, we propose asking what actor groups are involved, what they consider good and fair for school education, what kind of ‘generalizable’ knowledge they require to

handle uncertain situations, what rhythms and time horizons they bring to the table, in what regards our perspectives as scholars imply critical or affirmative relations to other actors' views, and how digital research tools facilitate or complicate our research tasks. All these aspects have important consequences for our methodological choices and for the roles we play vis-à-vis current initiatives in the digital transformation of education.

Our reflection areas emerge from connecting three fields of scholarship that have so far been only loosely linked: improvement studies in education, pragmatist epistemology, and critical EdTech studies. We believe each field would benefit from intensifying this exchange. For improvement studies, our argument addresses an important gap: while existing frameworks provide either methodological recipes or structures for stakeholder collaboration, orientations integrating both dimensions while remaining sensitive to digital contexts are currently lacking. For pragmatist epistemology, the reflection areas demonstrate both the potential and the need to concretize epistemological principles for methodological decisions in digital contexts. For critical EdTech scholarship, we add a neglected dimension: how change-oriented researchers can navigate digital complexities without sacrificing either critical stance or practical relevance.

The digital transformation simultaneously changes what we study, how we study it, and the social configurations in which research takes place. Our seven reflection areas provide leverage points for navigating the resulting complexities – not as prescriptive solutions, but as invitations to deliberate engagement with methodological challenges that are too easily overlooked in everyday research practice.

This pragmatist shift toward reflexive and adaptive methodology points to broader tasks for the field. Among them are developing new quality criteria for change-oriented research suited to digitally transformed environments and fostering communities for methodological exchange where researchers can share experiences navigating these challenges. The goal is not methodological standardization but cultivating reflexive practice that acknowledges the entanglement of methodology, politics, and digital transformation in contemporary educational research.

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